

INJURIES OF THE MEMBERS OF THE EYES

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Abstract: The division of damage to the organs of vision into damage to the surrounding tissues and damage to the eyeball is largely conditional, because the eyelids, tear organs and conjunctiva, muscle and conjunctiva Damage to other structures of the eye can cause damage to the eye in various degrees. In the article, the classification, prevention, and treatment methods of injuries of the organs of vision were studied and analyzed.

Key words: Eye diseases, eyeball, eye infection, central nervous system diseases, eyelid.

INTRODUCTION

Eye diseases - diseases of the eyelid, lid, conjunctiva, lacrimal organs and eye cup. Nearsightedness and farsightedness, eye astigmatism are also eye diseases. Eye diseases are congenital and acquired, infectious and non-infectious, acute and chronic, in one or both eyes. General diseases of the body: infectious (tuberculosis, wounds, rheumatism, influenza, diphtheria, typhus, etc.), parasitic (caused by various helminths, mas, echinococci), endocrine (diabetes, etc.), vascular (hypertensive disease, etc.) , blood diseases (leukemia), tumors (cancer, sarcoma, etc.), diseases of the central nervous system (meningitis, brain tumor), as well as the spread of the pathological process in the nasal cavity cause eye diseases. Eye infections, mechanical, chemical (acids and alkalis) and physical (heat, light, radioactive light) damage also cause eye diseases.

In diseases such as glaucoma, trachoma, severe eye damage and burns, the optic nerve can become blind if not treated in time. Ophthalmology studies the causes, treatment and prevention of eye diseases.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The division of damage to the organs of vision into damage to the surrounding tissues and damage to the eyeball is largely conditional, because the eyelids, tears and blood vessels, muscle and eye damage to other structures of the eye can cause damage to the eye in different degrees. Damage to the eyeball and surrounding tissues is divided into blunt (contusions), penetrating, non-piercing, and burns. It should be noted that under certain conditions, the cornea can be affected by cold with all substances (similar to a burn). Any eye injury, no matter how insignificant, requires urgent and conditional vision of an ophthalmologist. Eye damage varies in all regions of the republic and occurs in 1-4 cases per 1000 people. The level of eye damage depends on the population's age, sex, season and place of residence, and preventive measures. Eye injuries are 2 times more common among the urban population than among the rural population. Among eye injuries, 80% of microtraumas are permanent injuries, 10% are non-transitory, 2% are transversal, and 6% are burns.

In children's eye diseases hospitals, 60% are non-transmitted, 30% non-transmitted, and 10% are caused by burns. (E.I. Kovalevskii) Most of the patients with eye injuries, except for microtraumas, are admitted to the ophthalmology departments of hospitals or dispensaries with urgent instructions. All patients with penetrating eye injuries must be hospitalized as soon as possible. A quick notification is drawn up for each patient with an eye injury and sent to the statistics department of the health care department at the place of residence. In addition, a message will be sent to the heads of farms where the damage occurred. Blunt injuries of the eyeball and surrounding tissues (contusions) Blunt injuries of the eyeball and surrounding tissues include hyperemia, edema, hemorrhage, erosions, damage and dysfunction of the related accessory apparatus of the eye (ptosis, tears leakage etc.) is characterized by Blunt injuries are divided into 4 levels of severity: 1-mild, 2-medium, 3-severe, 4-very severe. Almost any blunt

injury is manifested by pain of varying duration, more or less. Blunt injuries in the eye socket can cause bleeding into the retrobulbar space, fractures of the bones of the eye socket and nasal walls.

As a result, symptoms such as swelling and absorption of the eyeball, hesitancy, and emphysema of the eyelids may occur. As a result of damage to the muscles that move the eye, it can be observed that the eye moves in different directions and that there is limited or no mobility on the side of the damaged muscle. In rare cases, a severe blunt injury to the eyelid leads to damage to the upper slit of the eye, which subsequently leads to external and internal ophthalmoplegia. First aid for damage to the tissues around the eye consists of applying a cold burn to the damaged area for 1-2 seconds. The doctor should quickly give preparations that increase blood coagulability and constrict blood vessels (vicasol, vitamin K, ascorutin, 10% solution of calcium chloride, suprastin). The patient should be sent to an ophthalmologist without delay, regardless of the severity, location, distribution of damage to the tissues around the eye. Consequences of blunt injuries: in 1st degree injury - recovery; In the 2nd degree injury - the eye function is almost unchanged, there are small residual changes; Level 3 - major morphological and functional changes; Level 4 - gross morphological changes, loss of activity. The severity of blunt eyeball injury is roughly divided into 3 levels: mild, medium, and severe. More often there are 1st degree, i.e. mild injuries, which pass without a trace in 3-5 days after treatment (in 90 percent of cases). It is not difficult to diagnose and assess the severity of blunt injuries, and first of all, changes in visual function (visual acuity, vision), changes in the front of the eye (cornea, depth of the anterior chamber) rality, fluid clarity, colored membrane and condition of the pupil), the size of the ophthalmotonus, as well as pain on palpation. The most common form or complication of blunt injury is corneal erosion.

It is characterized by the loss of clarity in the field of erosion and the lack of

light of the cornea (dullness). Especially when the corneal epithelium is stained with 1% sodium fluorescein, the result (defects) is clearly visible, in which they take on a light green color. Blunt injury manifested by sharp contusion, in addition to hemorrhage, can cause rupture or rupture of the colored membrane (iridodialix), rupture or rupture of the choroid and retina, retinal detachment, atrophy of the optic nerve, and total disruption. . All manifestations of this pathology, depending on the size and localization of the injury, primarily affect the state of central and peripheral vision, and even lead to blindness. The first aid of a doctor in the case of a blunt injury of the eyeball consists of the following: In addition to the first aid indicated for the contusion of the surrounding tissue, antibiotic or sulfanilamide solution for the conjunctival sac, if available, anesthetics (novocaine, dicain, lidocaine) as well should drip. A light aseptic bandage is poured and the patient is sent to an ophthalmologist without delay. The task of the ophthalmologist includes determining the severity of the injury with modern methods and solving the problem of continuing treatment in the next outpatient or inpatient setting. Symptomatic, anti-inflammatory, regenerative, neurotrophic and anti-inflammatory treatments are performed in the hospital.

Injuries of the surrounding tissues of the eye and the eyeball. The injuries of the surrounding tissues of the eye are primarily visible wound surfaces, hemorrhages, hemorrhages, edema, and related organ dysfunction, as well as acute characterized by pain syndrome. The first aid before the doctor consists in applying an aseptic non-pressing bandage as quickly as possible and sending it to a special clinic. The first doctor's aid is to administer tetanus anatoxin, wash the wound with disinfectant solutions, drip antibiotic solutions, inject antibiotics under the muscle, apply an aseptic bandage. Morphological and functional results depend on the localization of the injury, as well as on timely and complete surgical procedures with plasticity and reconstruction. The injury of the eyeball can be penetrating and not penetrating. A non-cutting injury occupies a position

between an eye capsule injury and a blunt injury. Its diagnosis is carried out by such methods as a beak injury. Also, there is no fundamental difference in the provision of first medical care and special ophthalmological care and subsequent treatment. But there is a difference in the location of the wound and the nature of the wound. Its margins are aligned and it heals without sutures with primary closure. Instruction: quickly admit the patient to the eye hospital. The outcome of the treatment is usually good, but in case of a large non-crossing wound, sharp corneal clouding and incorrect astigmatism can be observed, which reduce visual acuity and cannot be corrected. A wound of any size and localization that crosses the eyeball is considered severe and infected.

The damage is simple and complex according to the depth - it is complicated when the internal structures of the eye are damaged or fall into a wound, and when a foreign object falls into the eye or when a secondary infection occurs. Diagnosing an eyeball injury is usually simple, anyone can do it, and it allows you to answer the question of whether or not the injury is penetrating. The main sign of a penetrating wound of the eye is an open wound or an adherent wound. If it is located in the corneal area, then almost always the anterior chamber of the eye is heavy or shallow, and there may be blood in it. In addition, the internal structures of the eye, colored membrane, gem, vitreous body may be compressed in the wound, and a sharp hypotony of the eye is detected. Visual acuity, if it can be determined in older children, is very low. If the wound is located in the scleral area, there will almost always be bleeding around the sclera. In the wound, the internal structures of the eye: ciliary body, choroid, retina, vitreous body, eyeball can be compressed. In case of scleral damage, the anterior chamber is deeper than normal, hypotonic when palpating the eye. Visual acuity may not change significantly. When suspecting a cut wound in different parts of the eye capsule, the anamnesis of the injury is mainly given. Anamnestic instructions also play a key role in determining the crossing wounds in the back of the eye.

CONCLUSION

Prevention of damage to the organs of vision is at the first level to reduce the level of eye damage and inflammatory diseases, improve their structures, and their active, massive and systematic prevention. Prevention of eye damage is not only the work of DEZ workers and heads, transport, vision organizations, but also the task of people themselves, their parents, teachers and educators. Prevention of eye damage involves 2 stages. The first stage is aimed at primary prevention, that is, it consists of carrying out comprehensive measures to prevent eye injuries among children at home, on the street, at school together with the wider community. These works consist of concrete and precise planning of works that are approved and distributed by the commission on injury under the authorities. The implementation of plans is carried out in the form of months or decades of combating injury at the regional level, in the conditions of districts and cities. One of such events is systematic general prevention. Such measures reduce eye injuries by 2-3 times and primarily reduce the incidence of penetrating injuries. The second stage of prevention, that is, secondary prevention, on the basis of early diagnosis and quickly active complex medical and surgical treatment, helps to prevent the following complications of penetrating injury: purulent and phacogenic uveitis, metallosis, eye hypotony and sympathetic ophthalmia. With the help of this secondary prevention, in recent years, the number of complications has been reduced and, most importantly, primary enucleation has been reduced by 5 times (up to 0.5%).

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